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ILAs and related schemes across the EU: the state of play

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YEARS
SHAPING LEARNING AND
SKILLS FOR EUROPE

Request for ReferNet on ILAs

- Request to ReferNet in early 2025
- Only selected countries provided full-description of the current status
- The information reported below is provisional (subject to further reviews)

Overview

Country	Type	Years	Indicative scale (yearly)
France	Full scale ILA	2019 – now	1.8 bEur, 1.3m trainings (2023)
Netherlands	Vouchers	2022 – 2023	~200mEur, 216k applications (2022)
Croatia	Vouchers	2022 – now	28mEur, 30k vouchers (2024)
Belgium (fl)	Account	2023 – now	~70mEur, 90% training leave (2024)
Lithuania	Limited ILA	2024 – now	~60mEur (total), 25k trainings (target)
Latvia	Limited ILA	2025 – now	~15mEur (total), 3.5k trainings (target)
Cyprus	Limited ILA	2025 – now	5mEur (total), 1.8k trainings (target)
Slovakia	To be operational by 2026.01		~16mEur (total), 5.000+14850 (target)
Greece	Not operational, but legislative framework in place		
Hungary	Not operational, no legislative framework, a completed TSI project		

Overview (cont.)

Country	Entitlement (Eur)	Eligible population
France	500/800 (up to 5.000/8.000)	16+, work experience
Netherlands	1.000/year	18-retirement, work experience
Croatia	Variable, average 987	15-retirement, not in education
Belgium (fl)	Voucher – 125; variable	Employees
Lithuania	500 for five years	18-65, employed, qualified
Latvia	500 (up to 1.000) + support	18+
Cyprus	2.400 for three years	Employed w. ISECD 1-3; LTU
Slovakia	200	16+ not in education
Greece	1.100/1.500 for two years	Unemployed; Employed
Hungary	n/a	n/a

Lessons learned and points for reflection in the schemes with implementation track-record (the analysis is not exhaustive)

The French CPF scheme

- The largest existing as well as highly inclusive scheme; particularly valuable lessons
- Debates on eligible activities, like the inclusion of non-professional certificate such as category B driving license, which represented 21% of courses in 2023
- Concerns by the employers' regarding autonomous choice by individuals/ the need to ensure labour market relevance and the unions regarding the co-payment
- Some concerns of price inflation (possibly concealed by shorter training duration)
- In response to rising costs and cases of fraud, a series of measures were introduced:
 - Secure identity verification via FranceConnect+ (mandatory since October 2022)
 - Large dereferencing of training providers in 2022
 - Ban on unsolicited commercial canvassing
 - Introduction of mandatory co-payment of 100 Eur, to be index to inflation

The Dutch STAP voucher scheme

- Replaced an existing tax incentive
- The scheme did not fully align with the ILA model, as it is not a universal entitlement and requires individuals to actively apply in order to benefit
- Implemented via quarterly calls with a budget ceiling and first-come, first-serve basis
- Some adjustments were made to address concerns such as misuse as well as that public funding should be used to reduce labour market shortages rather than directed toward personal interests
- However, due to saving needs and above-mentioned concerns, the scheme was discontinued after 2023.
- Further challenges, noted in relation to the scheme:
 - interaction with regional voucher schemes and local labour market infrastructure
 - limited financial scope and lack of measures supporting people facing barriers to learning participation

Croatian voucher scheme

- The scheme was considered successful and is seen as transitional measure towards an ILA-aligned system
- In total, 29,317 voucher requests were approved and 18,693 learners completed training programmes
- Most voucher users were employed (75%), with limited participation from disadvantaged groups
- An ILA model is foreseen to be developed between 2025 and 2029
- The main reported challenge of the voucher scheme is the insufficient involvement of unemployed individuals and other disadvantaged groups
- It is to be addressed via guidance, information and better integration with ALMPs

Belgian (fl) learning and career account

- An account combining several existing entitlements, including:
 - Paid training leave (up to 125 hours, extended in case of using Joint Right of Initiative), employer receives compensation of 21.30 Eur/hour
 - Training vouchers for employees providing a subsidy of 125 euros to spend on labour market or career relevant training, with mandatory 50% co-financing rate
 - Flemish educational credit, with private sector employees are entitled to 36 months of leave for training
 - Flemish care credit with public sector employees entitled to 18 months of full-time (or corresponding part-time) leave for training or care over the course of their career
- Largest part of the overall budget is represented by training leave scheme
- Main challenges relate to the inclusion of other existing schemes (e.g. for unemployed, sectoral schemes) and coordination with other initiatives, including at the federal level

Thank you

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